

A literature survey about potential global trends concerning youth cultures and urban space

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Aim of this short text is to collect a list of scientific publications that present research results relating to youth cultures characterised by alternative uses and representations of urban space, in order to facilitate international comparison and individuation of potential global trends.

The main focus is on skateboarding, graffiti writing and parkour (although also other phenomena have been taken into consideration), with reference to four main topics.

Section 1

The first topic is that of distinctive styles, that is to say of those practices shared by those individuals involved in each youth culture upon which collective identification processes are based.

With regard to this aspect:

- about skateboarding, see Hunter (2003) and Steyn (2004) for United Kingdom; Kelly (2005) for Canada; Yochim (2007) and Petrone (2010) for the United States; Bradley (2010) for Australia
- about in-line skating, see Dickson & Pollack (2000) for the United States
- about parkour see de Carvalho & Pereira (2008) on Portugal
- about graffiti, see Simões & Campos (2017) about Portugal; Alberto, Bittencourt & Domingues (2021) about Brazil.

Section 2

The second topic is that of normalization processes, through which societies try to bring these uses and representations back within the boundaries they define of what can be considered lawful.

With regard in particular to the building of dedicated places:

- about skateparks, among the earliest works, see L'Aoustet & Griffet (2001) referring to France; Owens (2001) referring to the United States; Freeman & Riordan (2002) about New Zealand; Dumas & Laforest (2009) referring to Canada; Bradley (2010) referring to Australia; La Mendola & Sterchele (2010) about Italy; Márquez & Díez García (2015) about Spain; O'Connor (2016) referring to Hong Kong; Bäckström & Sand (2019) referring to Denmark and Sweden; Holsgens (2019) referring to Korea; Zhang & Chan (2022) about China.
- about parkour parks see Gilchrist & Wheaton (2011), referring to the United Kingdom; Ameel & Tani (2012) about Finland; Lesné, Gibout & Lebreton (2019) about France; Højbjerg Larsen (2022) about Denmark.
- about bouldering plazas see Beekmeyer (2013), referring to Australia.

Focussing instead on institutionalisation, professionalisation, creation of competitions, commercialisation, but also on the use of the practice in education and urban regeneration:

- as regards parkour, considering institutionalisation see Lombard 2010, Wheaton & O'Loughlin (2017) about the United Kingdom, Sterchele & Ferrero Camoletto (2017) about Italy, Greenberg & Culver (2019) about Canada and the United States, and Højbjerg Larsen (2022) about Denmark; considering its use in education see de Sena and de Lemos (2020) about Brazil; as regards urban regeneration see De Martini Ugolotti (2017) with reference to Italy; about its commercialisation see Lombard (2010), Stapleton & Terrio (2012)
- as regards skateboarding and urban regeneration, see Howell (2005) for the United States, Glover et al. (2021) for Canada, Book & Svanborg Edén (2021) for Sweden, Riffaud (2021) for a transversal analysis; concerning competitions, see Lorr (2005) and Batuev & Robinson (2018) for the United States, Honorato (2013) for Brazil, Bäckström & Blackman (2022) for a global perspective; considering its use in education see Armbrust & Lauro (2010) about Brazil; with reference to professionalisation, see Snyder (2011) & Nichols (2021) about Canada and United States, Li (2022) about China, and Ferrero Camoletto, Genova & Marcelli (2023) about Italy

- with regard to graffiti, focussing on urban regeneration see Arroyo Moliner & Clavell (2016) about Spain, Chang (2018) about Singapore, Vaslin (2018) about France and Germany, da Silva Bastos, Guimarães & Docampo (2022) about Brasil, Cercleux (2022) about Romania, Parker & Khanyile (2022) about South Africa, and Zhang & Chan (2022) about China; concerning commercialisation, see Lombard (2013) and Diallo (2014) about United States, Ribeiro, de Sevilha Gosling & da Silva (2016) about Brasil, Rabiega & Burger (2017) about South Africa, Campos & Leal (2021) about Brasil, and Weill (2022) for a general perspective; considering its use in education see Al Lily & Alzahrani (2015) about Saudi Arabia.

Section 3

The third topic is that of control, of the the strategies through which any spontaneous forms of practice not sufficiently aligned with those institutionally defined are intercepted and sanctioned:

- referring to parkour, see De Martini Ugolotti & Moyer (2016), De Martini Ugolotti & Silk (2018), De Martini Ugolotti (2022), with reference to Italy
- referring to skateboarding, see Nolan (2003) for Australia, Nemeth (2006), Tsikalas & Jones (2018), Shobe & Conklin (2018) for the United States; Woolley, Hazelwood & Simkins (2011) and Dickinson, Millie & Peters (2022) for the United Kingdom; and O'Keeffe & Jenkins (2022) for Australia
- as regards graffiti, see Iveson (2010) and Lombard (2013) for the United States; Evered (2019) for Turkey; Fischer & Durr (2020) for New Zealand; and Iveson & McAuliffe (2022) for Australia.